

CHARACTERISTICS OF ORGANIZING INDEPENDENT EDUCATION

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7636710>

Abstract. *It is known that in the establishment of independent education, the task is not only to increase the knowledge, skills and qualifications of students in a specific subject, to form an independent worldview in them, but also to form creative research and scientific thinking in the student as a future specialist. should be found. Creative technological approach in this process requires quick thinking and active action from the student. That is the authors of this article intended to work on characteristics of organizing independent education atmosphere among in the process of higher education.*

Keywords: *education, independent activity, student, methods, lesson.*

The main goal of the reforms implemented in our republic is to ensure the well-being of the people, the peace and prosperity of the country, the development of the Motherland, and to take its rightful place in the world community. For this, the need to train competitive, qualified, business-minded, socially active specialist personnel in the labor market is a fact of life that does not require proof. From this point of view, a great responsibility is assigned to the mentors today. Because the successors of our nation are the future of our country, and it is a huge task for teachers and educators to bring up the young generation, who are the future of our country, as well-rounded mature people in all respects, and to give them education in accordance with world standards. Also, the basis of the "Law on Education" is the training of young people who are competent, talented, modern, and possess high spirituality.

Professors and teachers of the "Methodology of Primary Education" department of Gulistan State University take seriously the independent work of the student, which is part of independent education, and have developed a set of assignments "Student's independent work" from all subjects of the department. In the independent education of students of all subjects, the main focus is on the organization of his universal, cultural and personal, spiritual qualities. This is a general indicator of a highly qualified professional. Issues of teachers' assistance in the process of independent education and knowledge acquisition of students, issues of promotion and organization of study methods of advanced requirements of the experience of mastering subjects in our university were carefully considered, and several seminars were organized on this topic together with teachers of our university and teachers of the general secondary education system.

It is known that in the establishment of independent education, the task is not only to increase the knowledge, skills and qualifications of students in a specific subject, to form an independent worldview in them, but also to form creative research and scientific thinking in the student as a future specialist. should be found. Creative technological approach in this process requires quick thinking and active action from the student. Because the scientific organization of work and efficient use of the time budget will be realized only if student activity turns into creative activity. Then the student can focus on a specific object based on his interests.

Creative technological activity is not just an easy process. A person's intuition and perception are connected with psychological operations such as his memory and the scope of logical thinking. In creative activity, the student's knowledge is further improved with innovative skills and competencies. As a product of analytical thinking, the student:

- bring out the necessary ideas, rules and definitions from the content of the text;
- promote his ideas based on innovative approaches;
- to know the causal connections specific to learning and creative activity, determining certain qualities and characteristics in it, quality to quantity or quantity to quality, factors determining their consequences;
- it is necessary to conduct statistical-mathematical analyzes according to the obtained data bank and to be able to sort his opinion according to importance and make it into a specific system.

The EEES interactive method also has a special place in the performance of written control tasks. This can be expressed in the form of a table in the following form.

EEES table

T/p	TASKS	RESULT
1	EEES	answers
1.	E- express your opinion	
2.	C- explain the reason	
3.	M- examples	
4.	Y- summarise	

The student gives oral answers to the written assignments. In this case, based on the chain method of interactive methods, the teacher can express the final opinion in the order of the sequence of answers. Brainstorming, debate, 6x6x6 methods are used in the next stages.

In accordance with the independent education plan, the teacher should gradually give theoretical assignments to the student, and not all at once, it should be done on the principle of going from easy to complex according to the level of mastery of the student. Here, following simple arithmetic, it is necessary to correctly divide "average", "good" and "excellent" learners into microgroups, gradually increasing the complexity of tasks, and in the order of transition from traditional methods to interactive methods. The student's independent opinion is first formed within the microgroup, and then referred to the collective judgment

In order to turn TMI into an active form and content of education, the university educational and methodical council is carrying out a number of systematic works, in particular, internal normative documents of instructions for TMI have been developed.

In the guidelines, the following types of TMI are taken into account and the hours allocated to them are clearly defined, and a system for increasing the responsibility of departments and professors has been developed for practical application:

- TMI is organized in the auditorium using advanced pedagogical technologies;
- a set of independent work questions and tasks for audience topics with differentiated options. They are distributed to students and form an independent work outside of class;
- TMI prepared cases based on the topics given in the program;
- a method of working on each subject has been developed;
- Independent assignments for laboratory, seminar, and practical training were developed;
- supervision and course work (projects) are provided;

- separate assignments are given for practice;
- rating control is clearly indicated;

In the process of independent work, students develop: independent study skills, creative abilities grow, practical skills are formed, and the quality and efficiency of education increases.

The effectiveness of TMI largely depends on the pedagogical skills of professors, material and technical support (auditorium fund, educational and scientific laboratories, computers, educational literature fund, educational-methodical and information support, guidelines and normative documents) and the formation of students' interest and needs for independent work. . TMI training is carried out in five stages.

Stage 1. Goal setting. In this case, students should independently achieve the goals based on the task assigned to them, or they should set a specific goal. The teacher helps the students to determine the set of activities, materials and time needed to set their goals and gives their advice.

Stage 2. Planning. Students determine the necessary stages individually or in groups, the availability of equipment and didactic materials is checked. The teacher gives his advice to the students on how to find the necessary sources of information, and depending on the need, he can give them the information he needs.

Stage 3. Decision making. Students test that they have the theoretical knowledge to carry out their work based on their plans, using the test questions provided in the methodological instructions for carrying out the work. The teacher identifies possible errors and shortcomings in the decision and gives his advice to the student on how to eliminate these errors and shortcomings.

Step 4. Implementation and monitoring (monitoring). Students perform the work in accordance with their work plans and the order of work presented in the methodical instructions for the implementation of experimental work and monitor their actions and the results they achieve. The teacher intervenes in the students' work processes only if they significantly deviate from the set goal path.

Step 5. Evaluation. In this case, the students themselves give an initial assessment of how the task was completed. For this, they fill in the assessment sheets prepared by the teacher. These grades are then reviewed by the teacher and may be adjusted as needed.

So, if the knowledge is independently realized, felt, learned by facing difficulties, then this knowledge will be fully and deeply mastered. All of this will depend on responsibility for the studied subject, skills in academic activities, effective use of time in work planning, self-control, error correction, etc. With this, it will be possible to develop the independent educational activities of future specialists, to ensure the commonality of educational and scientific work, to attract students to research work, and on the basis of this, it will be possible to improve the quality of training of mature specialists.

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